

HEALTH PROFESSIONALS' KNOWLEDGE OF BREAST CANCER RISK FACTORS

OJIEABU Winifred Aitalegbe

Department of Clinical Pharmacy and Biopharmacy, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Background: Breast cancer ranks as the fifth cause of death from cancer overall and is still the leading cause of cancer mortality in women.

Objective: To assess knowledge of breast cancer risk factors and impact of practice duration among health professionals in a tertiary health institution in Ogun state.

Methods: A cross sectional descriptive prospective study which assessed 162 female health professionals on their knowledge of breast cancer. The data was analyzed using SPSS package version 16.0.

Results: The study population comprised doctors (9.3%), nurses (78.4%), Pharmacists, radiographers and lab scientists (12.3%) with mean age of 32.97 ± 0.92 . The practice durations of the respondents ranged from 0 – 10 years (46.3%) and above 30 years (9.9%). The doctors demonstrated higher knowledge in most of the areas as compared to the other groups as well as in the overall mean knowledge while the nurses had the poorest knowledge across board. In regards to risk factor in breast cancer, Doctors had a higher knowledge (100%) than the other groups in response to the question: Early menarche and late menopause is a risk of developing breast cancer (p-value=0.001).

Conclusion: Continuous education programme aimed at improving the risk factor knowledge among healthcare providers should be given more attention.

KEYWORDS: Knowledge, breast cancer, female health professionals, tertiary health institution

Received for Publication: 21/03/13

Accepted for Publication: 18/05/13

Correspondence: natbelpharmacy@yahoo.com

Background

Breast cancer ranks as the fifth cause of death from cancer overall and is still the leading cause of cancer mortality in women [WHO 2012, Jemal et al., 2007].

It is a disease that affects both developed and developing countries. In Nigeria, it has been reported to be the 2nd largest cause of death [Adebamowo and Ajayi 2000]. While breast cancer incidence has been shown to have stabilized or to be decreasing in some western countries, breast cancer burden has steadily increased in many developing countries with traditionally low incidence rates [Parkin et al., 2008, Adebamowo and Ajayi 2000]. The burden, however, is not equally distributed as the burden of breast cancer is growing in the developing world while declining in the West [Bhurgri et al., 2007, Ravdin et al., 2003]. In a recent study on Knowledge of risk factors, beliefs and practices of female healthcare professionals towards breast cancer in a tertiary institution in Lagos, it was observed that excluding doctors, knowledge of breast cancer risk factors among female healthcare professionals was poor [Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009]. An earlier study in Lagos, Nigeria, also found unsatisfactory level of knowledge about breast cancer risk factors among nurses [Odusanya and Tayo 2001]. Lack of awareness, amongst most women, regarding common presenting symptoms or breast cancer risk factors translate to poor breast cancer screening practices [Han et al., 2000, Maxwell et al., 1998].

The aim of this study was to ascertain the level of knowledge of health care professionals regarding risk factors in breast cancer.

Methods

The population of this study comprised of female health professionals in Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital (OOUTH), located in Sagamu, Ogun State. The categories of female health professionals included medical doctors, pharmacists, nurses, radiographers and laboratory scientists. Of the 170 copies of questionnaire administered 162 were retrieved giving a 95%. There was no strict parameter on the choice of female health professionals that were given the

questionnaire apart from the fact that they were currently employed by the management of the institution and also that they were on duty at the time of the study. Males, females that were on vacation, other casuals, administrative staff members and those who refused to participate were excluded from the study. Consent to administer the questionnaire was obtained from the appropriate authorities of the hospital before its administration. Maximum confidentiality of information was assured by excluding the names of the respondents or any information that could be linked to anybody.

Questionnaire design

This was a cross-sectional descriptive prospective study and the primary instrument for the collection of data was a pre-tested, self-administered questionnaire developed by the researchers. Questions were partly drawn using information on breast cancer from the literature text. Additional questions were adapted after modifications from questionnaires used in similar studies conducted previously in the country. The questionnaire was divided into 3 sub-sections namely demographic information of the respondents, knowledge of risk factors in breast cancer among the professionals and knowledge based on duration of practice.

Analysis

Responses to questionnaire were entered into Microsoft Excel for sorting and SPSS version 16 was used for further analysis. Data was analyzed using descriptive and comparative analyses. At 95% confidence interval, any P value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

Respondents' demographics characteristics

Out of the 170 questionnaires administered to the respondents, 162 were correctly filled and retrieved, giving a percentage of 95% retrieval. The study population comprised doctors (9.3%), nurses (78.4%) and Pharmacists, radiographers and lab scientists (12.3%). The mean age of the respondents was 32.97 ± 0.92 (mean $\pm$ SEM). The married percentage was 76.5 while 78.4% practiced Christianity as a religion. The practice durations of the respondents ranged from 0 – 10 years (46.3%) and above 30 years (9.9%) (Table 1).

Participants' knowledge of risk factors in breast cancer based on categories

In regards to risk factors in breast cancer, Doctors had a higher knowledge than the other groups in response to the questions to all the questions asked except response to: Infertility or late child bearing is a risk for developing the disease where the P/L/R had a higher percentage (70%) with statistical significance and Prolong breastfeeding does not increase the risk of breast cancer where nurses had higher knowledge (76.3%) with no statistical significance. The nurses had the poorest knowledge across board on almost all questions asked as well as the poorest response (37%) to a question. There was no statistical significance in the overall knowledge of risk factor based on categories $X^2=15.416$ $df = 2$ p value=0.075 (Table 2).

Participants' knowledge of risk factors in breast cancer based on duration of practice

Statistical difference was seen in the response to: delayed first pregnancy is a risk for developing breast cancer (p value=0.004) with those who had practiced for 0-10years duration having a higher percentage of 52 while those with between 21-30years in practice having the highest percentage (87%) in the response to: prolong breastfeeding does not increase the risk of breast cancer (p value=0.000) and those with 11-20years in practice had the highest percentage (52.7%) in response to the question: drinking alcohol may increase risk of breast cancer (p value=0.024). Those who had practiced for above 30years had a higher knowledge in only one response to all questions. However, there was no statistical significance in the knowledge that family history of breast cancer is a risk factor for developing breast cancer with a correct knowledge of 85.3%, 94.5%, 87.5%, 81.2% for those who have practiced for 1 -10, 11 -20, 21 -30 and above 30 years respectively. Based on duration of practice, there was no statistical significance in the overall knowledge of risk factors with $X^2=2.504$ $df =3$ p value=0.412 (Table 3).

Table1: Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents

Profession	Doctors	Nurses	Pharmacist/ Lab scientist/ Radiographer	Total (%)
	15 (9.3)	127(78.4)	20(12.3)	162(100)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
<i>Age</i>				
20 – 30 years	2 (1.2)	37 (22.8)	11 (6.8)	50 (30.9)
31 – 40 years	7 (4.3)	43 (26.5)	6 (3.7)	56 (34.5)
41 – 50 years	3 (1.9)	26 (16.0)	3 (1.9)	32 (19.8)
51 – 60 years	3 (1.9)	11 (6.8)	-	14 (8.6)
Above 60 years	-	10 (6.2)	-	10 (6.2)
Mean Age ± SEM = 32.97 ± 0.92				
<i>Marital status</i>				
Married	12 (7.4)	101 (62.3)	11 (6.8)	124 (76.5)
Single	3 (1.9)	26 (16.0)	9 (5.6)	38 (23.5)
<i>Duration of practice</i>				
0 – 10 years	7 (4.3)	53 (32.7)	15 (9.3)	75 (46.3)
11 – 20 years	5 (3.1)	45 (27.8)	5 (3.1)	55 (33.9)
21 – 30 years	3 (1.9)	13 (8.0)	-	16 (9.9)
Above 30 years	-	16 (9.9)	-	16 (9.9)

Table 2: Participants knowledge of risk factors in breast cancer based on categories

	Doctors (n=15) Number (%)	Nurses (n=127) Number (%)	P/L/R (n=20) Number (%)	Total (162) Number (%)	p-value
RISK FACTOR					
Early menarch and late menopause is a risk of developing breast cancer	15 (100.0)	61 (48.0)	10 (50.0)	86 (53.1)	0.001
Infertility or late child bearing is a risk for developing the disease	10 (66.7)	58 (45.7)	14 (70.0)	82 (50.6)	0.055
Delayed first pregnancy is a risk for developing breast cancer	10 (66.7)	47(37.0)	10 (50.0)	67 (41.4)	0.062
Women who have become pregnant more than once or become pregnant at an early stage have reduced risk of having breast cancer	9 (60.0)	64 (50.4)	12 (60.0)	85 (52.5)	0.602
Taking oral contraceptive pil increases the risk of breast cancer	12 (80.0)	98 (77.2)	14 (70.0)	124 (76.5)	0.739
Prolong breastfeeding does not increase the risk of breast cancer	10 (66.7)	97 (76.3)	13 (65.0)	120 (74.1)	0.441
Drinking alcohol may increase risk of breast cancer	12 (80.0)	62 (48.8)	10 (50.0)	84 (51.9)	0.072
Increase in age is a risk factor of developing breast cancer	12 (80.0)	72 (56.7)	10 (50.0)	94 (58.0)	0.166
A family history of breast cancer increases the risk of breast cancer	15 (100.0)	112 (88.2)	16 (80.0)	143 (88.3)	0.191

P/L/R = Pharmacists, lab scientists and radiographers

Table 3: Participants correct knowledge of risk factors in breast cancer based on duration of practice

knowledge of risk factors in breast cancer	0 - 10 years(n=75) Number (%)	11 - 20 years(n=55) Number (%)	21 - 30 years(n=16) Number (%)	Above 30 years(n=16) Number (%)	p-value
Early menarch and late menopause is a risk of developing breast cancer	41 (54.7)	27 (49.1)	7 (43.8)	11(68.8)	0.464
Infertility or late child bearing is a risk for developing the disease	43 (57.3)	26 (47.3)	5 (31.3)	8 (50.0)	0.261
Delayed first pregnancy is a risk for developing breast cancer	39 (52.0)	23 (41.8)	4 (25.0)	1 (6.25)	0.004
Women who have become pregnant more than once or become pregnant at an early stage have reduced risk of having breast cancer	40 (53.3)	29 (52.7)	10 (62.5)	6 (37.5)	0.550
Taking oral contraceptive pil increases the risk of breast cancer	59 (78.7)	45 (81.8)	11 (68.8)	9 (56.3)	0.154
Prolong breastfeeding does not increase the risk of breast cancer	62 (82.7)	40 (72.7)	14 (87.5)	4 (25.0)	0.000
Drinking alcohol may increase risk of breast cancer	45 (60.0)	29 (52.7)	7 (43.8)	3 (18.7)	0.024
Increase in age is a risk factor of developing breast cancer	49 (65.30)	32 (52.2)	6 (87.5)	7 (43.8)	0.124
A family history of breast cancer increases the risk of breast cancer	64 (85.3)	52 (94.5)	14 (87.5)	13 (81.2)	0.322

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of this study group about breast cancer risk factors was above average with the doctors demonstrating higher knowledge in most of the areas as compared to the other groups (nurses, pharmacists, laboratory scientists and radiographers (P/L/R)) This is consistent with earlier studies [Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009, Ahmed *et al.*, 2006]. The nurses demonstrated the least knowledge as per breast cancer risk factors which are consistent with earlier reports [Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009, Oluwatosin and Oladepo 2006]. This is unexpected among the nurses since they come more frequently in contact with patients than the P/L/R group. With regards to duration of practice, the saying that 'Practice makes perfect' did not hold waters here as those with the least period of practice had higher knowledge while the group with the longest practice duration had the least knowledge. This is in contrast with the study of [Ahmed *et al.*, 2006] where clinical experience did not seem to influence knowledge or practice. The knowledge of this study group on early menarch and late menopause being a risk factor of developing breast cancer was found to be higher than those of previous ones carried out in two states of Nigeria [Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009, Oluwatosin and Oladepo 2006]. An average of 88% of the respondents believed that a family history of breast cancer increases the risk of developing breast cancer, a result which is similar to that obtained in a study [Yeliz *et al.*, 2011] but higher than that obtained in another study [Akhigbe and Omuemu, 2009]. There was however contrasting results with Yeliz *et al.* [Yeliz *et al.*, 2011] in the area of contraceptive use where this present study recorded higher knowledge among the respondents. Delayed first pregnancy as a risk factor for developing breast cancer was the lowest correct respondents' knowledge but was higher than that found in some earlier studies [Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009, Oluwatosin and Oladepo 2006]. Increase in age as a risk factor in breast cancer was identified by 58% of the respondents, a low figure when compared with a similar study by Ibrahim and Odusanya [Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009]. People are likely to develop a positive healthy behaviour if there is perception of some risks and this is one of the responsibilities of majorly health professionals.

There was no statistical significance in the overall knowledge of risk factor of breast cancer based on the professional groups with p-value 0.075. This is in contrast with the earlier study in Lagos where participants' profession was found to be associated with the level of knowledge of breast cancer risk factors [Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009]. The mean knowledge of the respondents to risk factors of breast cancer was 60.7% with an overall mean score of 0.61 ± 0.49 . This is in contrast with the results obtained from a similar study carried out in Benin where majority of the respondents had a very poor knowledge about the risk factors for breast cancer with an overall mean knowledge of 1.61 ± 0.93 [Akhigbe and Omuemu, 2009]. Several risk factors have been identified to developing breast cancer, thus adequate knowledge

of risk factors and avoidance of such factors or avoidance of lifestyle that triggers off the disease is very important in prevention of breast cancer. Knowledge of risk factors can also promote screening and diagnosis procedures for individuals who have risks that cannot be modified or changed by lifestyle thus improving clinical presentation when the disease occurs. Thus knowledge of breast cancer risk factors by health professionals could help in proper patient guidance [Stojadinovic *et al.*, 2011, Koçak *et al.*, 2010].

The poor knowledge recorded among pharmacists, lab scientists and radiographers is similar to the earlier findings in a study in Benin [Okobia *et al.*, 2006]. This defect in knowledge may be understandable since the P/L/R may not have had the opportunities mostly enjoyed by the doctors and nurses through diagnoses and care of patients. If these categories are to be included as role models for providing knowledge base about breast cancer, an enlightenment and orientation programmes could be introduced in form of seminars or mandatory continuous professional development as part of the general health maintenance.

A recent study from Malaysia [Devi *et al.*, 2007] found that training health care workers to improve their skills in cancer detection, coupled with raising public awareness, resulted in about a 50% reduction in stage III and IV cancers of the breast and cervix, at a comparative low program cost.

CONCLUSION

The doctors demonstrated higher knowledge in most of the areas as compared to the other groups (nurses, pharmacists, laboratory scientists and radiographers (P/L/R)) and the overall mean knowledge score when compared to earlier findings is commendable and impressive. This may be due to the increasing awareness, orientation and campaign programmes carried out by various health bodies, International, government and non-governmental organization against the upsurge and uprising of breast cancer among women and society at large. This level of knowledge should be maintained and improved upon. More efforts should therefore be directed at educating the female health professionals most especially the nurses, pharmacists, lab scientists and radiologists who are in the best position to educate their gender about this disease and its various risk factors.

Potential Conflicts

The author declares no competing interests.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to thank the female health workers in the facility used who participated in the study.

REFERENCES

- Adebamowo CA, Ajayi OO.(2000). Breast cancer in Nigeria. *West Africa Journals of Medicine*19:179–91.
- Ahmed F, Mahmud S, Hatcher J, Khan SM. (2006). Breast Cancer risk factor knowledge among nurses in teaching hospitals of Karachi, Pakistan: a cross sectional study. *BMC Nurs*5:6.doi:10.1186/1472-6955-5-6.
- AkhigbeAO and Omuemu VO. (2009). Knowledge, attitudes and practice of breast cancer screening among female health workers in a Nigerian urban city.*BMC Cancer* 9: 203.
- Bhurgri Y, Kayani N, Faridi N, Pervez S, Usman A, Bhurgri H, et al. (2007) .Pathoepidemiology of breast cancer in Karachi '1995-1997'. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev* 8: 215-20.
- Devi BCR, Tang TS, Corbex M. (2007).Reducing by half the percentage of late-stage presentation for breast and cervix cancer over 4 years: a pilot study of clinical down staging in Sarawak, Malaysia. *Ann Oncol* 18(7): 1172e6.
- Han Y, Williams RD, Harrison RA. (2000). Breast cancer screening knowledge, attitudes, and practices among Korean American women. *Oncol Nurs Forum* 27: 1585-91.
- Ibrahim NA and Odusanya OO. (2009). Knowledge of risk factors, beliefs and practices of female healthcare professionals towards breast cancer in a tertiary institution in Lagos. *BMC Cancer* 9:76.

- Jemal A, Ward E, Thun MJ. (2007). Recent trends in breast cancer incidence rates by age and tumor characteristics among U.S. women. *Breast Cancer Res* 9(3): 28.
- Koçak S, Çelik L, Özbaş S, et al. (2011). Risk factors in breast cancer, risk assessment and prevention: 2010 Istanbul consensus meeting report. *The J of Breast Health*7: 47-67.
- Maxwell AE, Bastani R, Warda US. (1998). Misconceptions and mammography use among Filipino-and Korean-American women. *Ethn Dis* 8: 377-84.
- Odusanya OO and Tayo OO. (2001). Breast Cancer knowledge, attitudes and practice among nurses in Lagos, Nigeria. *Acta Oncol* 40(7): 844-848.
- Okobia MN, Bunker CH, Okonofua FE, Osime U. (2006). Knowledge attitude and practice of Nigerian women towards breast cancer; a cross sectional study. *World Journal of Surgical Oncology*4: 11.
- Oluwatosin OA and O Oladepo. (2006). Knowledge of breast cancer and its early detection measures among rural women in Akinyele Local Government Area, Ibadan, Nigeria *BMC Cancer* 6: 271.
- Parkin DM, Sitas F, Chirenje M, Stein L, Abratt R, Wabinga H. Part I. (2008). Cancer in indigenous Africans—burden, distribution, and trends. *Lancet Oncology* 9(7): 683–92.
- Ravdin PM, Cronin KA, Howlader N, Berg CD, Chlebowski RT, Feuer EJ, et al. (2007). The decrease in breast-cancer incidence in 2003 in the United States. *N Engl J Med* 356:1670-4.
- Shiyam K, Ayesha MI, Nauman FM, Nehal M. (2009). Knowledge, attitude and preventive practices for breast cancer among Health Care Professionals at Aga Khan Hospital Karachi. *J Pak Med Assoc* 59(7): 474-478.
- Stojadinovic A, Summers TA, Eberhardt J, et al. (2011) Consensus recommendations for advancing breast cancer: risk identification and screening in ethnically diverse younger women. *J Cancer* 2: 210-27.
- World health organization.(2012). Cancer; *factsheets* Copyright © WHO. Available from <http://www.who.int/cancer>.
- Yeliz YA, Zeynep B, Melis N, Iskender G, Fevziye C. (2011). Knowledge, attitude about breast cancer and practice of breast cancer screening among female health care professionals: a study from Turkey. *Asian Pacific Journals of Cancer Prevention*12: 3063-3068.
-

